

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices / IPBES transformative change assessment (4.4)

Code: IPBES_TCA_4.4

Versioning 02: (21.10.2024)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10252304

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 4 should address challenges that include inertia, including personal (e.g., habits and mind sets), sociocultural (e.g., norms) and systemic (e.g., market failures, rules, institutions, global monitoring and enforcement). The chapter provides evidence on unsustainable production and consumption patterns and individual habits and practices as challenges to transformative change. In this context, a review of literature focused on this challenge was conducted and is further described below as feeding into section 4.2.4.

Process overview

miro

Protocol

The evidence to inform challenge 4 on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices was gathered through four processes. Following the searches conducted below, some references were added and cited in the chapter section based on comments received in the second external and additional review processes as suggested by reviewers.

Process 1: Literature reviews for Section 4.2.4 - Human migration and consumption and production patterns

Four searches were done using different combinations of keywords related to human migration and consumption and production patterns. The search engines used for all searches were SCOPUS and Google Scholar and all searches were carried out in English.

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic reviews using SCOPUS; non-systematic literature search using relevant keyword combinations in Google Scholar
- **Search terms:**

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( biodiversity OR ecosystem* OR nature OR environment* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "human migration" OR "human movement" ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( barrier* OR obstacle* OR challenge* ) ) AND ( EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "COMP" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ENGI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MEDI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BIOC" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATH" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHYS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CHEM" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "IMMU" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CENG" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BUSI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "HEAL" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ECON" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NEUR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHAR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NURS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "VETE" ) )
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- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS (systematic) and Google Scholar (non-systematic)
- **Sample extracted:** 123 results **(A)**; based on a reading of the titles and abstracts, 32 found to be relevant for the assessment **(B)**.

Details search 2:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic reviews using SCOPUS; non-systematic literature search using relevant keyword combinations in Google Scholar
- **Search terms:**

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( biodiversity OR ecosystem* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( rail* OR road* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( barrier* OR obstacle* OR challenge* ) ) AND ( EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ENGI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "COMP" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BIOC" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BUSI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MEDI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATH" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHYS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CHEM" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CENG" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "IMMU" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NEUR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "HEAL" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHAR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "VETE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NURS" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "re" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ch" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "cp" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "bk" ) )
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- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS (systematic) and Google Scholar (non-systematic)
- **Sample extracted:** 882 results **(C)**; based on a reading of titles and abstracts, 180 found to be relevant for the assessment **(D)**.

Details search 3:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic reviews using SCOPUS; non-systematic literature search using relevant keyword combinations in Google Scholar
- **Search terms:**

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( biodiversity OR ecosystem* OR nature OR environment* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( unsustainable ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( consum* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( barrier* OR obstacle* OR challenge* ) ) AND ( EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BIOC" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BUSI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CENG" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CHEM" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "COMP" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "DECI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "DENT" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ECON" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ENGI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "HEAL" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "IMMU" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATH" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MEDI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NEUR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NURS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHAR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHYS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "VETE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "EART" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ARTS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PSYC" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "re" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ch" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "cp" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "bk" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ed" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "dp" ) )
```

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS (systematic) and Google Scholar (non-systematic)
- **Sample extracted:** 178 results (**E**); based on a reading of titles and abstracts, 113 found to be relevant for the assessment (**F**).

Details search 4:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic reviews using SCOPUS; non-systematic literature search using relevant keyword combinations in Google Scholar
- **Search terms:**

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( biodiversity OR ecosystem* OR nature OR environment* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( unsustainable ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( produc* ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( barrier* OR obstacle* OR challenge* ) ) AND ( EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BIOC" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "BUSI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CENG" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "CHEM" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "COMP" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "DECI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "DENT" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ECON" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ENGI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "HEAL" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "IMMU" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MATH" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "MEDI" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NEUR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "NURS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHAR" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PHYS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "VETE" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "EART" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "ARTS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA , "PSYC" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "re" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ch" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "cp" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "bk" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ed" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "dp" ) )
```

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS (systematic) and Google Scholar (non-systematic)
- **Sample extracted:** 335 results (**G**); based on a reading of titles and abstracts, 189 found to be relevant for the assessment (**H**).

The material that was finally selected for reviewing was based on a reading of the titles and abstracts of all the search results. Those that were completely irrelevant to the topic at hand despite using the keywords and the filters were rejected right away. If the abstracts or the titles revealed any material to be relevant, they were read in their entirety to determine if they talked of the issues of interest as barriers or challenges or obstacles to biodiversity safeguarding. If the papers simply referred to any of these issues in general or provided an overview of them but not in the context of being challenges or barriers or obstacles, they were deemed unsuitable for Chapter 4.

Process 2: Section 4.2.4 - Waste and chemicals

Details Search 1 - Chemicals management:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** specific and systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TITLE-ABS-KEY ((biodiversity OR nature OR ecosystem* OR "ecosystem service*") AND ("chemical* management") AND (barrier OR challenge OR "overcome*" OR "transform*")) AND PUBYEAR > 2009 AND PUBYEAR < 2024
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS
- **Sample extracted:** 12 records
- **Treatment applied:** The content of the title, abstract and the complete content of the articles was screened. 4 articles were excluded because they were not related with the addressed issue. 8 articles were considered relevant for the assessment.

Details Search 2 - Waste management:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** specific and systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**
TITLE-ABS-KEY (((biodiversity OR nature OR ecosystem* OR "ecosystem service*") AND ("waste management*") AND (barrier OR challenge OR "overcome*" OR "transform*"))) AND PUBYEAR > 2009 AND PUBYEAR < 2024 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re"))
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS
- **Sample extracted:** 1037 records
- **Treatment applied:** the records were screened based on the content of the title, abstract and a complete content of the articles found in the search implemented. 1005 articles were excluded because they were not related with the addressed issue (these articles were related to technical descriptions about waste management). In sum, we found 1037 results; based on a reading of titles, abstracts and the complete contain, 32 articles were considered relevant for the assessment.

Extracted results are presented in document (I).

Process 3: Section 4.2.4 - Telecouplings

This scoping review addresses focuses on investigating by case examples how telecouplings, i.e. flows of material, humans, finance, values, knowledge, etc. may act as barriers to transformative change. The work followed principles of a scoping review¹.

¹ Eklipse. (2020). Bridging the gap between policy and knowledge on biodiversity in Europe.

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review for abstracts and titles of articles found in Web of Science, obtained through one search string, leading to an initial list of 105 records.
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search terms:**

TS=(telecoupling* AND (biodiversity OR ecosystem*))

- **Search engine:** Web of Science
 - **Exact search date:** 1 December 2023
 - **Sample extracted:** 105 records (**J**). From this list, five case studies were selected that were complementary in investigating different types of telecouplings (related to trade, tourism, animal migrations and human migrations) and in the complexity of telecouplings (from simple to more comprehensive cases)
 - **Treatment applied:** Information was analysed by applying the criteria presented in Chapter 4's Table 2. Results of the analysis are presented in the same Table and within Challenge #4 of Chapter 4 of the Transformative Change Assessment.
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Process 4: Section 4.2.4 - Habits

The evidence to inform this section was gathered through three processes

Process 1: References based on expert-knowledge

Based on expert knowledge, a number of relevant publications (journals and books) were selected to structure the corresponding subsection.

Process 2: Searches using search strings based on specific words or concepts

To complement the references that were included based on expert knowledge (see process 1), two searches were done using different combinations of specific concepts related to barriers to transformative change. The purpose of these searches was to define the main concepts used in this chapter of the assessment. The search engine used for these searches was Web of Science, as it allows for the most advanced combination of search terms and search results. All searches were carried out in English.

Searches were done in steps. First, the terms were searched by topic (searches title; abstract; author; keywords; and Keywords plus). The details of the searches are described and only search terms and the final samples (of relevant publications used to inform challenge 4, section on habits and its corresponding supplementary material) are presented below.

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

(TS=(habits)) AND (TS=(sustainability)) AND (TS=(change)) AND (TS=barrier))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Sample extracted:** 60 publications **(K)**
- The author of this section read the sample to select relevant publications, which resulted in a final bibliography of 12 publications **(L)**.

Details search 2:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search of publications
- **Search terms:**

(TS=(habits)) AND (TS=(sustainability)) AND (TS=(change)) AND (DT=(review article))

- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Sample extracted:** 62 publications **(M)**

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(A)	CSV	405 KB	123 results from the Scopus and Google Scholar search on human migration
B	2_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(B)	CSV	85 KB	32 selected results from the Scopus and Google Scholar search on human migration
C	3_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(C)	CSV	3 252 KB	882 results from Scopus and Google Scholar search 2 on human migration
D	4_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(D)	CSV	617 KB	180 selected results from Scopus and Google Scholar search 2 on human migration and consumption and production patterns
E	5_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(E)	CSV	477 KB	178 results from Scopus and Google Scholar search 3 on unsustainable consumption
F	6_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(F)	CSV	303 KB	114 selected results from Scopus and Google Scholar search 3 on unsustainable consumption
G	7_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(G)	CSV	931 KB	335 results from Scopus and Google Scholar search 4 on unsustainable production patterns
H	8_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(H)	CSV	540 KB	189 selected results from Scopus and Google Scholar search 4 on unsustainable production patterns
I	9_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(I)	CSV	29 KB	Records extracted from Scopus search on waste and chemicals management
J	10_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(J)	CSV	505 KB	105 records from Web of Science search on telecouplings
K	11_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(K)	PDF	69 KB	51 publications extracted from Web of Science search 1 on habits
L	12_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(L)	PDF	160 KB	List of 12 publications selected from Web of Science search 1 on habits
M	13_IPBES_TCA_4.4_11-2023_(M)	PDF	70 KB	55 publications extracted from Web of Science search 2 on habits